

D7.2 - DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (v2)

Work package	WP7 Project Management
Task	T7.4 Ethical adherence and data management
Due date	31/10/2025
Submission date	06/02/2026
Deliverable lead	PEDAL Consulting
Version	V3.0
Authors	Gabor Mester, Robert Miskuf (PEDAL)
Reviewers	All partners

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	29/09/2025	Draft version distributed for partners' input	PEDAL
0.2	10/10/2025	Partners' input	ALL PARTNERS
	20/10/2025	Full draft for revision	PEDAL
0.2	21/10/2025	Revision	UNIT
0.3	27/10/2025	Format revision	UNIFE
0.4	29/10/2025	Pre-Final version for submission	PEDAL
1.0	30/10/2025	Final version	UNIT
2.0	05/02/2026	Revision upon the PO's comments	PEDAL
3.0	06/02/2026	Revised version submission	UNIT

Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright notice: © 2022 - 2025 SUSTRACK Consortium

Deliverable information		
Nature of the deliverable:		*DMP
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	x
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SUSTRACK project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

DMP: Data management plan

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

SUSTRACK Consortium:

#	Participant Organization Name	Short Name	Country
1	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA UNITELMA SAPIENZA	UNIT	IT
2	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
3	KNOWLEDGE SRL	KE	IT
4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC	SK
5	DBFZ DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH	DBFZ	DE
6	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGENT	BE
7	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TECNALIA	ES
8	FVA SAS DI LOUIS FERRINI & C	FVA	IT
9	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	UNIFE	IT
10	BUNDESANSTALT FUER MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND - PRUEFUNG	BAM	DE
11	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS	CIRCE	ES

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are a **crucial element** of good data management as they provide the description of its life cycle, following the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) data principle. DMPs **include information** on:

- How the data will be handled (how it will be described, managed and stored) both during and after the end of the project;
- What data will be collected, processed and/or generated by the project;
- Which methodology and standards will be used;
- Whether data will be shared/made open access and;
- How data will be protected and preserved (including after the completion of the project).

This document presents the updated version of the SUSTRACK Data Management Plan (DMP), prepared as D7.2 (T7.4, WP7 “Project Management”). Building on the initial DMP submitted in Month 6, this revised version incorporates the experience gained during project implementation, updates on data collection and processing activities, and refinements to ensure alignment with FAIR principles and Horizon Europe requirements.

As a living document, the DMP evolved alongside the project, reflecting new datasets, updated methodologies, and lessons learned from ongoing activities. This updated version consolidates the final state of SUSTRACK’s data management practices and provides a framework that ensures all data generated, collected, processed, and re-used was handled transparently, securely, and in a way that maximises its scientific, societal, and policy relevance.

In line with the project’s objectives and expected outcomes, SUSTRACK involved multiple activities that required systematic data collection, generation, processing, and validation across scientific, policy, and stakeholder engagement dimensions. To guarantee reliability and reproducibility, datasets were securely stored immediately after collection or generation, as well as after processing.

The purpose of this final DMP is to provide the consortium with a consolidated and harmonised framework for data management throughout the SUSTRACK project. It defined common rules and practices for the collection, documentation, storage, preservation, and sharing of project data. Metadata standards were consistently applied (e.g. author, date, affiliation, version, title, revisions, access rights, and storage details), ensuring that datasets were findable, interoperable, and suitable for long-term preservation.

By following these practices, the consortium strengthened internal communication, ensured full compliance with ethical and legal requirements (including GDPR), and maximised the value and re-use potential of SUSTRACK data. As a result, the project's datasets have been made accessible and usable for policymakers, researchers, industry stakeholders, and society at large, contributing to both the scientific knowledge base and evidence-based policymaking in support of the transition to a sustainable circular bioeconomy.

This document includes the description of:

- Data types and how this data was collected, processed, maintained and shared during and after the end of the project;
- FAIR data management;
- Data Security;
- Preferred repositories to archive published data
- Metadata and vocabulary
- Social, Ethical, Legal, and Privacy concerns.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	Introduction	11
2.	Data summary	14
2.1	Purpose of data collection/generation and its relation to the project objectives	14
2.2	Types and formats of collected/generated data	16
2.2.1	Data collected/generated through direct input methods	17
2.2.2	Data collected/generated from dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement and exploitation activities.....	23
2.2.3	Data collected/generated from project management and coordination	25
2.2.4	Data collected/generated from the development and use of the GEM.....	26
2.3	Origin of data and re-use of pre-existing data.....	26
2.4	Size of data	27
2.5	Data utility.....	29
3.	FAIR data	31
3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	31
3.1.1	Data discoverability and identification mechanism	31
3.1.2	Naming conventions	33
3.1.3	Search keywords.....	34
3.1.4	Versioning.....	35
3.1.5	Standards for metadata creation.....	35
3.2	Making data accessible.....	35
3.2.1	Openly available and closed data	35
3.2.2	Data accessibility and availability.....	37
3.2.3	Methods, software tools and documentation to access the data	39
3.2.4	Data, metadata, and data integrity.....	40
3.2.5	Restrictions.....	40
3.3	Making data interoperable.....	41
3.4	Increase data re-use.....	43

3.4.1 License schemes to permit the widest use possible	43
3.4.2 Availability for re-use	44
4. DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE	47
5. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS	48
5.1 KE Srl Green Economy Model (GEM)	48
6. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	49
6.1 Estimated costs for making data FAIR	49
6.2 Data management responsibilities.....	49
7. DATA SECURITY	52
8. ETHICS AND OTHER ISSUES	53
9. CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD	54
ANNEXES	55
Annex I Privacy Policy.....	55
Annex II Informed Consent Form	60
Annex III Data Subject Request Form	63
Annex IV Dataset Inventory.....	67

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 SUSTRACK Project Community profile on Zenodo32

Figure 2: CC BY-SA 4.043

Figure 3: CC BY 4.043

Figure 4: CC BY-ND 4.044

Figure 5: CC BY-NC 4.044

Figure 6: CC BY-NC-ND44

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Size of data.....27

Table 2: Data utility29

Table 3: Good practices for data anonymisation36

Table 4: Data accessibility.....37

Table 5: Dublin Core Metadata standard vocabulary42

Table 6: Expected time that data will be made open through Zenodo44

Table 7: Data management responsibilities of SUSTRACK's partners per data collected/generated under each WP50

List of Abbreviations	
AB	Advisory Board
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CS	(EU and CS level)
DCMI	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EUROSTAT	European Statistical Office
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEM	Green Economy Model
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IP	Internet Protocol
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISP	Internet Service Provider
KB	Kilobyte
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NAS	Network Attached Storage
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
PIDs	Persistent Identifiers
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

This document constitutes the final version of the Data Management Plan (DMP), prepared as Deliverable D7.2 of the SUSTRACK project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101081823.

The SUSTRACK consortium, composed of 11 partners across 6 European countries, adhered to sound data management principles throughout the project. All data collected, processed, and generated during the implementation were managed, archived, and preserved in accordance with the [Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template](#) and the FAIR principles. By following this framework, the consortium ensured that the project's datasets were systematically curated, safeguarded, and prepared for long-term accessibility and re-use.

Along these lines, this final version of the DMP aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Describe the data management life cycle for the data collected and/or generated in the framework of SUSTRACK, serving as the key element for good data management.
- Outline the methodology employed to ensure the sound management of the data collected, and/or generated as well as to make them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR).
- Provide information on the data that were collected and/or generated and the way in which they were handled during and after the end of the project, along with the standards applied to this end.
- Provide details on how the data were made openly accessible and searchable to interested stakeholders as well as their curation and preservation.
- Present information on the resources that were allocated to make data FAIR clearly identifying responsibilities pertaining to data management, while addressing data security and ethical aspects.

With the above in mind, this final version of the DMP is structured in 9 distinct chapters, as follows:

Chapter 1 presents the description of the SUSTRACK context and outlines the objectives and structure of the DMP.

Chapter 2 defines the purpose and objectives of the SUSTRACK activities leading to the data collection and generation processes. It also outlines data types and formats, origin and relevant stakeholders that might utilise them.

Chapter 3 describes the processes followed to ensure FAIR data management in the framework of SUSTRACK.

Chapter 4 introduces data quality assurance processes.

Chapter 5 describes the FAIR management of other research outputs (digital or physical) that were generated or re-used by the beneficiaries throughout the project.

Chapter 6 provides an overview of the resources that were used and the respective data management responsibilities.

Chapter 7 underlines the data security strategy followed by the SUSTRACK team.

Chapter 8 addresses ethical aspects involved under the scheme of SUSTRACK regarding the collected/generated data.

Chapter 9 concludes by summarising the outcomes achieved in SUSTRACK's data management and reflecting on the key lessons learned throughout its implementation.

The structure of the DMP was drafted in line with the European Commission's Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template, complemented by additional elements tailored to the specific characteristics of SUSTRACK. While initially conceived as a living document, the DMP was updated and refined over the course of the project to reflect newly generated data, methodological adjustments, and evolving consortium needs. This final version (D7.2, Month 36) consolidates all updates and provides a comprehensive overview of SUSTRACK's data management practices.

PEDAL Consulting (PC), as the lead partner for this deliverable, was responsible for the preparation and coordination of the DMP, with all consortium partners contributing to its continuous development and enrichment.

Annexed in the document are (i) the project's Privacy Policy (Annex I), the templates for the (ii) Informed Consent Form (Annex II) and (iii) the Data Subject Request Form (Annex III) which were used during the implementation of the project's activities to ensure compliance with relevant applicable EU and national regulation(s).

Key updates

This final version of the SUSTRACK DMP reflects the updates and refinements made since the initial version (D7.1, M6). As a living document, the DMP evolved throughout the project to capture changes in practices, tools, and responsibilities, ensuring continuous alignment with FAIR principles, Horizon Europe requirements, and GDPR compliance.

The main updates introduced in this version include:

- **Integration of Zenodo as the project's open repository:** A dedicated SUSTRACK Zenodo community was created to host openly available datasets, ensuring long-term preservation, assignment of DOIs, and enhanced discoverability.
- **Metadata standards:** Strengthened emphasis on metadata quality and consistency, including the adoption of Dublin Core standards for closed datasets and Zenodo's metadata schema for open datasets.
- **Expanded stakeholder engagement data:** Additional details on the collection and management of datasets from dissemination, communication, and stakeholder engagement activities (e.g., events, website analytics, newsletter subscriptions).

- **Ethics and GDPR compliance:** Updated templates for the Informed Consent Form and Data Subject Request Form, and confirmation that no transfer of personal data outside the EU occurred.
- **Security measures:** Clearer procedures for risk-based data protection, including backup policies, integrity checks, and access control protocols for closed datasets.
- **Conclusion and legacy:** A consolidated reflection on lessons learned during the project and the long-term value of the Sustrack Zenodo community for supporting future research, policy, and innovation.

2. DATA SUMMARY

To achieve its objectives, SUSTRACK collected, generated, and re-used data categorised as non-sensitive, i.e. not belonging to any special categories¹ of personal data as defined under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR²).

This final version of the DMP summarises how data management was implemented across the project. It describes the purpose of the data collection and generation activities undertaken, outlines the main types and formats of data produced, and details their origins. It also reports on the estimated and actual size of datasets and highlights their utility and re-use potential for different stakeholder groups.

By following the procedures set out in the initial version of the DMP, the consortium ensured transparency, consistency, and compliance with the FAIR principles. All datasets were systematically documented with metadata, securely stored, and where appropriate, prepared for long-term preservation and open access. This process has maximised the usability and impact of SUSTRACK data for policymakers, the scientific community, industry stakeholders, and civil society.

2.1 Purpose of data collection/generation and its relation to the project objectives

The purpose of the data collection was to help achieve the successful fulfilment of the main objectives of the SUSTRACK project, with specific actions requiring data collection and generation:

1. **Gap analysis.** A desk analysis was conducted with a specific focus on the selected case studies. The analysis aimed at reviewing the main findings from the existing literature and recent EU surveys on trends with respect to the environmental, economic and social limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy as well as the barriers to this transition under cultural, economic, environmental, governance, structural, and technical dimensions.
2. **Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy.** Findings were discussed and validated during a co-creation focus group with 15 Quadruple Helix stakeholders. The preliminary results and 20 interviews with experts were incorporated into a survey to consolidate the findings.

¹ Special categories of personal data according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation) include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

² Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>. Last accessed: 7/10/2025

3. **Prioritising identified barriers.** The AHP and ANP methods were then used to produce a list of priorities and interdependencies based on expert judgements and consensus at online interviews and surveys involving 20 participants.
4. **Review of knowledge** to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems. Existing knowledge (in terms of indicators, data, methods and models) that addresses circularity and sustainability aspects at different levels, were reviewed and operationalised into the SUSTRACK monitoring tool to foster their practical usability/uptake.
5. **Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition.** Desk research to address critical (research) gaps and develop knowledge and recommendations on how to fill those gaps.
6. **Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis.** Cases were selected from four sectors that have been identified as facing critical challenges within the current linear system: (a) the construction sector;(b) the textile sector; (c) the (fine) chemical sector and (d) the plastic sector.
7. **Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations from the 11 case studies.** For every case study a factsheet was produced. These factsheets were published in one deliverable (report D3.3). The results of the case studies have also been generalised to provide input to the policy factsheets, as well as to derivate conclusions and recommendations for the four bio-based sectors.
8. **Development and calibration of the Green Economy Model.** Data required for the parameterization and calibration of the Green Economy Model were sourced from various databases. The simulations served for the analysis of cross-sectoral impacts of the transition scenarios and provide insight into the systemic impact of policies
9. **Development of policy portfolio scenarios** formulated scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, that defined the final input requirements. The data sources include official statistics, policy documents, scientific papers and further literature in the context of bioeconomy at the national and EU level. A workshop with stakeholders utilized to present and verify the scenarios.
10. **Model simulation and validation of the results.** A variety of scenarios were simulated, considering the implementation of sectoral targets both in isolation and in conjunction with others.
11. **Capacity building for local stakeholders.** Stakeholders at the national and regional levels involved in the 11 case studies were empowered through capacity-building workshops (online). The stakeholders' responses supported the analysis of potential pitfalls and opportunities of policy instruments for the implementation of transition paths, based on their contextual specificities.
12. **Identification of policy priorities.** Based on the literature review, first, a revision of policy-related opportunities and barriers for the sustainable transition took place to prepare the identification of policy priorities. Selected policy options were validated in co-creation workshops during the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences,

framing them within the context of the four selected sectors. Finally, a prioritisation survey was applied.

13. Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition to a circular bio-based economy.

A set of recommendations were provided based on the identified policy priorities, and policy instruments of importance for sectorial stakeholders derived from the co-creation workshops. The recommendations include indications of pressing actions (roadmap) and considerations for a sustainable transition at the national and EU level. Preliminary validation of proposed recommendations has been discussed with stakeholders during the IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences.

14. Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK's Advisory Board. The representatives of the stakeholder community of contributors, multipliers and adopters constituted the advisory board.

15. Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences. These activities connected stakeholder feedback with the project results through engagement activities, considering all perspectives.

16. Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities of SUSTRACK with a view to measuring their results and impact, fine-tuning SUSTRACK's Dissemination and Communication Plan, as well as fulfilling the project's reporting requirements towards the Commission.

17. Collaboration with Related Networks and Initiatives to benefit from synergies with other relevant EU initiatives and to establish close collaboration with the project. Concluded projects: STAR-ProBio, STAR4BBI, BIOMONITOR, Pilot4U. Ongoing projects: BIOTRANSFORM, STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, HARMONITOR, CALIMERO, ALIGNED, BIORECER, 3-CO , CEE2ACT, Circular Cities and Regions Initiative, BIORADAR, ROBIN, BIO2REG, CheMatSustain, ESCIB, SYMBA, ShapingBio, BioFairNet, ARGONAUT, BOOST4BIOEAST, BEAMING, MainstreamBio, BioINSouth, SYMBIO, INNOVATE-EU, COPilot and European Bioeconomy Network.

2.2 Types and formats of collected/generated data

SUSTRACK has set out to collect/generate data of various structures and formats. Along these lines, the data definition process used for this DMP is based on the source and the physical format of the data³. In particular, we defined two main aspects: (i) the process under which the underlying data are created/captured which includes electronic texts documents, spreadsheets, questionnaires and transcripts, among others and (ii) the storage format of quantitative and qualitative data. Examples of this aspect include easily accessible formats, such as post scripts (e.g. pdf, xps, etc.), machine-readable formats (xml, html, etc.), spreadsheets, (e.g. xls, csv, etc.), text documents (e.g. docx, rtf, etc.), compressed formats (e.g. rar, zip, etc.) or any other

³ Jakobsson, U., Braukmann, R., Lundgren M., Expert Tour Guide on Data Management. Retrieved from <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/1.-Plan>.

format required by the objectives and methodology of the activity within the framework of which is produced.

Under this framework, special attention was paid to using open **formats**⁴ (such as csv, pdf, zip, etc.) and/or **machine-readable formats**⁵ (such as xml, json, csv, rdf, etc.) when possible, to enhance the **interoperability and re-use of data**. In doing so, we were providing data that is **easily readable and freely usable in any software program** employed by third parties interested in utilizing the data.

The type and formats of the data collected/generated in the context of SUSTRACK can be divided into 4 categories, namely (i) data collected/generated by direct input methods, (ii) data collected/generated from dissemination, communication, clustering and exploitation activities, (iii) data collected/generated from project management and coordination, (iv) data collected/generated from the development and use of the Green Economy Model as described in the following subsections.

2.2.1 Data collected/generated through direct input methods

Direct input methods, under the scope of SUSTRACK, involve methodologies for collecting data through desk research and interactions between consortium partners and external stakeholders, with the latter providing data to the former. Along these lines, external stakeholders undertake the role of a data subject which is a natural person whose personal data is being processed⁶. In particular, the identification and selection of suitable data subjects are based on purposeful sampling according to which, internal and external stakeholders are identified and selected by consortium partners. This is based on their role regarding the finetuning the SUSTRACK approach through localised validation activities and co-create policy recommendations (i.e., policy makers, business leaders, authorities, action groups, civil society, NGOs, etc.) and the objectives of the respective activity for which data is collected. In this context, quantitative and qualitative data were collected/generated during SUSTRACK:

Within this framework, SUSTRACK collected and generated both quantitative and qualitative data. Quantitative data included numerical information derived from surveys, statistical sources, and structured questionnaires. Qualitative data comprised interviews, written contributions, workshop minutes, and various forms of stakeholder feedback. Together, these datasets provided the evidence base for assessing the environmental, social, and economic limits of the linear fossil-based economy and for developing policy recommendations supporting the transition to circular, bio-based systems.

⁴ According to the [Open Data Handbook](#): “An open format is a file format with no restrictions, monetary or otherwise, placed upon its use and can be fully processed with at least one free/open-source software tool and it is not encumbered by any copyrights, patents, trademarks or other restrictions so that anyone may use it”.

⁵ According to the [Open Data Handbook](#): “Machine readable formats are file formats that can be automatically read and processed by a computer. Machine-readable data must be structured data”.

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>.

- **Quantitative data** is numerical and acquired through counting or measuring⁷. Examples of quantitative data are the yearly turnovers of a business, the hourly compensation of a worker, the number of SMEs in Europe, etc. This data may be represented by ordinal, interval or ratio scales and lend themselves to statistical manipulation.
- **Qualitative data**, sometimes referred to as categorical data, is data that can be arranged into categories based on physical traits, gender, colours or anything that does not have a number associated with it⁸. Moreover, written documents, interviews, and various forms of in-field observation are all sources of qualitative data. Examples of qualitative data are the preferences of learning, skillsets, country of origin, etc.

Additional details with respect to the different types and formats of data that were collected through direct input methods under the frame of SUSTRACK are provided below:

1. **Gap analysis.** A desk analysis was conducted by UNIT and other supporting partners to extract the main findings from the existing literature (T1.1). This involved a review of high-quality scientific articles in high-impact academic journals and well-known databases of peer-reviewed literature (e.g., Web of Science, Science Direct), as well as renowned and influential studies and reports published in the grey literature (e.g., government and industry reports, reports and deliverables of related projects). Information was also retrieved from active EU projects (e.g., STAR4BBS, BIORECER, BRANCHES, TRANSITION2BIO, GENB, BIOGOV.NET), the EC Knowledge Centre and recent EU surveys on trends in limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy as well as the barriers to this transition under cultural, economic, environmental, governance, structural, and technical dimensions. The data collected was mainly **qualitative** in nature with descriptive texts and then they were deposited and analysed in excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). After the analysis, the gathered information was used to prepare a text document (.docx and .pdf) as D1.1 (M6), as well as a [scientific publication](#) for the Journal of *Sustainable Production and Consumption*.
2. **Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy.** For identifying and consolidating the challenges faced by the linear, fossil-based economy, related to environmental, economic and social sustainability aspects, as well as technical, structural and cultural barriers, different stakeholder activities have been implemented. First, findings obtained in the previous task were discussed and validated during a co-creation focus group (organised by PEDAL) with 15 Quadruple Helix (i.e., policy makers, industry professionals, researchers, NGOs, citizens) stakeholders from Europe, selected with the help of all partners (M8). The workshop was organized in the framework of the official EU Green Week 2023. Data generated during the event (e.g. minutes) were saved in the project repository. In addition, 20 interviews with experts (from at least 6 MSs) were conducted and the insights were incorporated into a survey (in English, sent to more than 400 stakeholders across the EU) to consolidate the key findings (M11). The results were shared and disseminated during the INSPIRE conference (M12). For each interview, a short summary was prepared and shared with the interviewed experts. In addition, the questionnaire and the results of the survey were saved in the project repository. Based on the results, reports have been prepared (.docx and .pdf) as D1.2 (M15). The results were also presented at the [SDEWES](#)

⁷ Neuman, W. L. (2014). Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches. Boston: Pearson.

⁸ Neuman, W. L. (2014). Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches. Boston: Pearson.

[Conference](#) (September 2024, Rome), and a scientific paper is currently under review at the time this report is prepared.

3. **Prioritising identified barriers.** The AHP was performed to prioritise the barriers validated through multi-stakeholder consultation activities. To evaluate the barriers, a survey was created through LimeSurvey, which allowed stakeholders to determine weights and make comparisons between them. In total, 20 responses were obtained, and the expert panel was composed of representatives from the general public (65%), construction sector (15%), chemical sector (10%), plastic sector (5%) and textile sector (5%). Then, the ANP method was used to identify interdependencies based on expert judgements involving the same 20 participants. After the analysis, the gathered information was used to prepare a text document (.docx and .pdf) as D1.3 (M18).
4. **Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems.** A desk analysis was led by TEC to identify research gaps in existing monitoring practice (T2.1). This involved a review of scientific articles, as well as studies and reports published in the grey literature (e.g., government and industry reports, reports and deliverables of related projects). Information was retrieved from past and active EU projects (e.g., BIOMONITOR, STAR4BBS, BIORECER etc.), the EC Knowledge Centre. The data collected concerned the type of indicators, data and methods currently used to assess and monitor bioeconomy. These were mainly qualitative in nature with descriptive texts and then they were deposited and analysed in excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). After the analysis, the gathered information was used to prepare a text document (.docx and .pdf) as D2.1 (M10).
5. **Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition.** This involved a review of scientific articles, as well as studies and reports published in the grey literature (e.g., government and industry reports, reports and deliverables of related projects), but also information gathering through interviews with stakeholders in the 4 case studies. So, the information collected were both qualitative and quantitative in nature and were deposited and analysed in excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). After the analysis, the gathered information was used to prepare two public documents (.docx and .pdf) as D2.2 (M20) and D2.3 (M32).
6. **Development of a framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition, including a dashboard for stakeholders.** This is based on outputs from T2.1 and T2.2 and from WP3 and WP4 and consists of:
 - a) A text document (.docx and .pdf) detailing the developed framework and monitoring tool. It includes user guidance and practical examples of how the framework can be used to assess and monitor sustainable transition towards bioeconomy (D2.4 (M36)).
 - b) A database (excel spreadsheet) of the data used to feed the SUSTRACK monitoring tool. These include the indicators repository and the data used for the country performance analysis.
 - c) The SUSTRACK monitoring tool, a web-based tool to assess and monitor bioeconomy.

7. **Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis.** BAM coordinated the selection of case studies used during the implementation of the SUSTRACK project. In total 15 case studies have been shortlisted and for each of them, a fact sheet has been prepared. They were included as public documents (.docx and .pdf) in D3.1 (M6).

8. **Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations.** This refers specifically to T3.3 (Case study analysis) and T3.4 (Analysis of finding and main conclusions) which both focussed on the case study work. The case study work was used to improve the indicator set and assessment methodologies (from WP2), provided guidance on pathways for changing and defining potential (policy) intervention options (related to WP4 modelling the future and WP5, best policy instruments involved). So, all this case study work generated a lot of knowledge in the form of qualitative data, outcomes of stakeholder exchanges in workshops, both qualitative and quantitative data and PowerPoints and factsheets with guidance to lead discussions and support the exchange of information. This generated a lot of data and insights (all included in working documents in .word and .xls format) which have all been systematically reported in two deliverables (reports .word and .pdf format). In D3.3 (M28) all case study assessment results were reported per case study. In D3.4 the overarching findings, recommendations and conclusions from the 11 case studies and four biobased sectors are presented (M30) again in the form of a .word/.pdf document.

9. **Development of policy portfolio scenarios.** The policy instruments and set measures were collected by all case study responsible, work package partners and further experts, using a template in an excel file. The descriptive part of the scenarios was presented as .docx/.pdf files. For the Workshop presentation a PowerPoint file (.ppt), as well as facilitation through a Miro board will be prepared.

10. **Capacity building for local stakeholders.** This task includes making accessible and usable for external stakeholders the materials and tools prepared in different stages of the project by the project partners in charge of their development. This includes the video tutorial on how to use the SUSTRACK monitoring tool, as well as the accompanying documentation that explains its use in text documents (.docx and .pdf) (D2.4). It also includes the tailored workshops delivered across selected countries during the DEPLOY conferences.

Guidelines for the identification and review of case study information (T3.2) as well as the conclusions and recommendation to the bio-based sectors (T3.4) were translated into user-friendly formats, according to the identified target groups of each of them, which were included text documents and presentations (.docx, .pdf and .pptx). Finally, the capacity-building materials prepared in publishable formats (.pdf) and model tutorials (.pptx) were be utilized in online webinars, allowing for a recording of the data produced (e.g. .mp4, .mpeg, .wmv).

- 11. Identification of policy priorities.** This refers specifically to T5.1 in which policy priorities have been identified to support the sustainable transition by reviewing the limits of the linear, fossil-based and carbon-intensive economy (WP1), as well as policy-related opportunities and barriers for the sustainable transition. This involved a systematic review of scientific and grey literature and especially results of former EU H2020 and BBI projects: e.g., BERST, S2BIOM, Power4Bio, Celebio, STAR-ProBio, STAR4BBI. Also, national policy data was collected in the 11 case studies of the project. All this information was included in excel (.xls) files and summarized in reports (.docx). The derived policy priorities and examples of good policies were also validated in the policy co-creation workshops that took place (INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences). This generated 12 PowerPoint presentations (.ppt). It also provided information collected through polls during the workshops (anonymous information) and workshop summary reports, which were included in the SUSTRACK deliverable reports (D5.1 and D5.2) and in summary factsheets presented in different forms on the SUSTRACK project website. Finally, an additional prioritisation survey was implemented to increase the number of stakeholders consulted to more than 200. Furthermore, this information was handled following privacy legislation, and all information was only published in a summarized manner in D5.3 in the form of tables in which answers can never be traced back to individuals. The survey data was processed in Excel files (.xls). This information was not published but only used for internal project purposes.
- 12. Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy.** This activity was based on the resulting data from WP1, WP3, WP4 and T5.1, in consideration of policies status-quo at the EU level and for the selected sectors and countries where the case studies are placed. Also, the data generated during the stakeholder engagement activities (e.g., co-creation workshops and from T5.2), which have a qualitative nature, were utilized for this activity. The consolidation of collected information, to point out policy priorities at the sectorial level and provide recommendations and guidelines to policymakers, was prepared in documents (.docx and .pdf) as well as presentation formats (e.g. .pptx).
- 13. Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK’s Advisory Board (AB).** The data regarding the setup of the SUSTRACK Advisory Board (AB) fell under Task 6.2 (PC) and included personal information of candidate AB members (e.g., name and surname, gender, organisation, position, email, country of placement, and a brief description of their professional profile). These data were collected by the consortium partners under the guidance of PC, following a structured process of retrieving information from publicly available online sources (e.g., professional websites, institutional pages, etc.). Each partner identified suitable and relevant stakeholders from their own networks and provided the consortium with publicly available information. The candidates were then evaluated through a selection process and formally approached to obtain their consent to join the Advisory Board. All related data were stored in text documents, image, and spreadsheet formats (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg).
- 14. Stakeholder Engagement activities, co-creation workshops and conferences.** This section referred to data collected through stakeholder activities and events conducted in the context of SUSTRACK, aimed at linking stakeholder feedback with the project’s results. The data collection comprised the EU-wide survey and interviews with EU citizens,

implemented by BAM and PEDAL, and disseminated through the INSPIRE, DESIGN, and IMPLEMENT conferences. All related data were stored in text documents, image, and spreadsheet formats (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg).

- a. The Co-Creation Workshops engaged selected stakeholders from industry, government, and project partners to identify policy priorities, define policy actions, and provide recommendations to policymakers in support of a sustainable transition. The resulting discussions, ideas, and feedback were fully documented and integrated into project outputs through written notes and customised guidelines stored in standard text document formats (.docx).
- b. All personal data collected during these activities were processed in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and used exclusively for research and stakeholder engagement purposes. Upon completion of the project, all personal data were either anonymised or securely deleted to prevent unauthorised access or further processing.

15. **Collaboration with Related Networks and Initiatives** to benefit from synergies with other relevant EU initiatives and to establish close collaboration with other projects. The data regarding collaboration with Related Networks and Initiatives fall under Task 6.3 (FVA), were reported under D6.2 and D6.4 (FVA) and included information on projects and initiatives and their key contacts (e.g. Project's Year, Call identifier, Call topic, Acronym, Coordinator, Cordis/website ID, Full title, Key Contact information, EuBioNet Membership). Data was collected by FVA through direct access to databases generated in previous projects. In particular, FVA EuBioNet and FVA contacts in the bioeconomy sector databases was used for the project's activities by FVA but was not shared among partners or be subject to further exploitation by the consortium. Stakeholders gave consent to involve them in other related projects. The data was stored in text documents (.docx or .pdf files), spreadsheet format (.xlsx, .csv files), presentations (.ppt files), audio-visual files (.mp4 files), and images (.jpeg or .png files). Additionally, basic data (name, acronym, brief description, contacts - which have been provided by the coordination with the permission to be published) about the projects are displayed in the "Sister Projects" section of the SUSTRACK website to increase the visibility and awareness of other EU-funded projects.

Data collected and generated through direct input methods were stored primarily in standard .docx and .xlsx formats. These formats enabled the structured documentation of information from various sources in a single location, allowing raw data from transcripts, as well as text, images, and other objects, to be consolidated into either a single document file or multiple tabs of a spreadsheet.

Whenever relevant, these files were converted into open and machine-readable formats (e.g. .xml and .csv) to enhance interoperability and re-usability. This ensured that the datasets produced within SUSTRACK remained consistent with FAIR principles, facilitating both internal use by consortium partners and potential re-use by external stakeholders.

2.2.2 Data collected/generated from dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement and exploitation activities

Data derived from the monitoring and assessment of dissemination, communication, clustering, and exploitation activities fell under the responsibility of WP6 (FVA and PC). These datasets included:

- i. analytics from the project website and social media accounts (YouTube, LinkedIn, Twitter/X);
- ii. data collected from project events;
- iii. data collected from dissemination and communication actions (e.g. participation in external events, project workshops, conferences);
- iv. newsletter subscription data; and
- v. data relating to the exploitation of project results.

The data were identified and collected through online analytics tools, social media accounts, and structured partner reporting. FVA provided the necessary templates (.docx, .xlsx) to all partners, together with clear guidelines on how to complete them, and collected inputs on an ad-hoc basis whenever dissemination or stakeholder engagement actions took place. FVA was also responsible for preparing periodic reports to evaluate the overall progress of dissemination and communication activities, measuring outcomes against pre-defined KPIs.

The storage formats used for these datasets included .csv, .docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .pptx, .mp4, .jpeg, and .png files. Where possible, machine-readable formats (e.g. .csv) were prioritised over proprietary formats to enhance interoperability, accessibility, and re-use.

Website and social media analytics

Website analytics:

Website analytics data were collected throughout the duration of SUSTRACK to monitor the visibility, outreach, and impact of the project's online presence. These data included indicators such as the number of visits, unique users, session duration, geographic distribution of visitors, and access to specific sections of the website. The data were collected through the website's analytics tools (e.g. Google Analytics) and were used exclusively for aggregate reporting and evaluation of communication and dissemination activities under WP6. No personal or sensitive data were stored, and all analytics were processed in compliance with GDPR requirements, ensuring that users could not be individually identified.

The resulting datasets were stored in .xlsx and .csv formats, allowing for both internal reporting and long-term accessibility. To ensure consistency, FVA periodically exported analytics reports, structured them in predefined templates, and shared them with consortium partners as part of dissemination performance monitoring. These datasets provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of SUSTRACK's communication channels and supported evidence-based decision-making for optimising outreach activities. They were archived together with other dissemination-related data and prepared in machine-readable formats to maximise re-usability for future reference and project evaluations.

Social media statistics (YouTube, Twitter and LinkedIn):

Social media analytics data were collected throughout the project to monitor and assess the performance of SUSTRACK's online dissemination and communication activities. The monitoring covered the project's official channels on YouTube, Twitter/X and LinkedIn, and focused primarily on quantitative metrics such as the number of followers, impressions, reach, engagement rates, and interactions with project content.

These data provided evidence of the effectiveness of SUSTRACK's communication strategy and were systematically analysed to identify trends, evaluate progress against dissemination KPIs, and propose adjustments to improve outreach and engagement. The analyses enabled the consortium to refine content, optimise timing, and strengthen connections with relevant stakeholder groups.

The raw data were stored in Microsoft Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx) and, where possible, exported into machine-readable formats (e.g. .csv) to support interoperability and re-use. The interpretative analyses of these results were reported in the deliverables in Word format (.docx). Together, these datasets and reports supported evidence-based monitoring of SUSTRACK's communication impact and were archived as part of the final project documentation.

Data collected from project events and stakeholder engagement activities

During the implementation of SUSTRACK, event-related data were collected both from events organised by the project (e.g. co-creation workshops, validation workshops, conferences, interviews, and other physical or virtual meetings) and from the participation of consortium partners in third-party events. For SUSTRACK-organised activities, participants' lists were compiled, including general demographic information such as name, surname, gender, organisation, position, country, and email address. For external events, partners reported on their participation and provided information on the event characteristics and outreach.

All personal data collected through event registrations were processed in full compliance with the GDPR. During registration, participants were informed about the purpose of data collection, how their information would be used, and their rights regarding access, correction, or withdrawal of consent. Explicit consent was obtained from participants before collecting and using their data. Only authorised project staff had access to this information, which was securely stored on servers and used exclusively for the purposes described in the project's Privacy Policy.

The collected data served multiple purposes: to monitor stakeholder engagement, assess the visibility and outreach of the project, and ensure consistent reporting across partners. In addition, participants who provided consent during registration were invited to subsequent SUSTRACK events and activities or included in the project's newsletter mailing list to receive updates on project results and opportunities for engagement.

The datasets combined quantitative information (e.g. number and type of participants, geographical distribution) with qualitative feedback (e.g. discussion topics, engagement outcomes). These data were updated each time a partner organised or attended an event. All data were stored in structured and secure formats such as .xlsx, .csv, .json, and .xml, ensuring consistency, interoperability, and long-term usability, while protecting the confidentiality of personal information.

All personal data collected during events were processed only for the stated purposes and, upon project completion, were securely deleted to prevent any unauthorised access, retention, or further processing.

Data collected from dissemination and communication actions

Dissemination-related data were collected through the periodic monitoring of SUSTRACK's diverse communication and dissemination activities, including publications in relevant journals, blog posts, press releases, social media content, website articles, interviews, participation in events (conferences, meetings, workshops), presentations, e-mails, seminars, and informal discussions. To ensure consistency, an **Excel-based template** was developed and shared with all partners, enabling them to log both recommended and executed activities. The template was also made available online, allowing partners to update their inputs directly and in real time. The purpose of collecting these data was to systematically assess the outreach, coverage, and effectiveness of dissemination efforts throughout the project's implementation. All contributions were consolidated into a single master file (.xlsx), providing a comprehensive and structured record of SUSTRACK's communication and dissemination performance.

Newsletter subscriptions

A subscription form hosted on the SUSTRACK website enabled the collection of contact details from stakeholders interested in receiving project updates. Through this sign-up form, stakeholders voluntarily provided their personal information to receive the project newsletter, which was issued once per year. The collected data consisted of a list of subscribers and included the following personal information: (i) email address, (ii) first and last name, (iii) country, (iv) type of organisation, (v) region, and (vi) gender. A copy of this contact list was securely stored on a dedicated cloud server managed initially by BlueiTech (<https://blueitech.com/>) and then by Hostinger, which were used to distribute newsletters and email campaigns. All personal data were processed exclusively for the purpose of providing updates on SUSTRACK's progress and events and were protected in accordance with BlueiTech's Privacy Policy and GDPR requirements. Subscribers were also informed about the management of their personal information through the privacy policy section of the SUSTRACK website, where details on data protection and rights of data subjects were made available. In addition, other subscribers were added to the mailing list after providing explicit consent through the registration forms of SUSTRACK events.

2.2.3 Data collected/generated from project management and coordination

During the implementation of SUSTRACK, data were collected from a variety of management and coordination activities. These included partners' internal communication, quality assurance processes, progress monitoring, risk analysis, and project workshops and events. The resulting datasets were both qualitative and quantitative in nature and took multiple forms, such as meeting minutes, written insights, reports documenting activity outcomes and progress, participant lists, and photographs capturing events.

The storage formats used for these data prioritised machine-readable formats (e.g. .csv) to enhance interoperability and re-use. Where appropriate, alternative formats such as .docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .ppt, .jpeg, and .png were also employed. This approach ensured that management and coordination data were systematically preserved, accessible to the consortium, and aligned with FAIR data management principles.

2.2.4 Data collected/generated from the development and use of the GEM

The development and calibration of the Green Economy Model required sourcing data for a wide range of socioeconomic and environmental key indicators. The World Bank Data Portal and Eurostat served as the main sources for macroeconomic indicators, including GDP (total and by sector), employment, and data from the System of National Accounts. Where data gaps were identified, as well as for forecasts on economic performance, supplementary information was retrieved from the World Economic Outlook database of the International Monetary Fund. For country-specific indicators not available in these primary sources, additional data were drawn from the public databases of national statistics offices.

The data used for parameter development and the validation of simulation results were stored in Excel spreadsheets (.xls, .xlsx, .csv) to ensure accessibility and re-use. Where the development of additional causal connections required further evidence, supporting information was obtained from scientific articles, reports, or studies, typically in .pdf format.

The Green Economy Model was also used to simulate baseline and transition scenarios, generating additional datasets for the analysis of policy impacts. Outputs from the modelling software (Vensim) were exported into Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx) for subsequent processing and analysis. Additional visual materials produced using Vensim were stored in image formats such as .jpeg and .tiff, ensuring that results were available both in structured data form and as visual representations to support communication and dissemination.

2.3 Origin of data and re-use of pre-existing data

In the context of SUSTRACK, new data were collected and generated by consortium partners as well as by external stakeholders actively participating in the project's activities. External stakeholder groups contributing to the generation of new data included the business community, public authorities, policymakers at regional, national, and EU levels, civil society organisations, researchers and academic experts, and other relevant actors. Their inputs provided valuable evidence for the project's validation activities, co-creation processes, and policy recommendations.

Alongside new data, SUSTRACK also relied on pre-existing datasets, results and knowledge. In particular, outputs from 30 EU-funded projects and initiatives such as STAR-ProBio, STAR4BBI, BIOMONITOR, BIOTRANSFORM, STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, 3-CO, HARMONITOR, CALIMERO, ALIGNED, BIORECER, and others, as well as relevant national initiatives, were integrated into the project's evidence base. These resources have been informing the SUSTRACK project throughout its duration, enabling the consortium to build on existing knowledge and avoid duplication of efforts.

Furthermore, consortium partners' internal expertise, accumulated through participation in previous European and national projects, directly and indirectly supported the implementation of SUSTRACK activities. This combination of newly generated data, existing project outputs, and partner expertise ensured a robust, comprehensive, and policy-relevant knowledge base for advancing the transition towards sustainable, circular, and bio-based systems.

2.4 Size of data

The following table (Table 1) summarises the activities implemented during SUSTRACK in which data were collected or generated. It provides an overview of the types and formats of the data, together with information on their size, thereby offering a consolidated view of the project's data landscape

Table 1: Size of data

No	Name of activity	Data	Type of data	Format of data	Size of data
1	Gap analysis	The literature gaps and trade-offs	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx .xlsx	1.97 MB 268 KB
2	Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy	Literature review, interviews, stakeholder event, survey.	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx .xlsx	500 KB
3	Prioritising identified barriers	Interviews and surveys	Text document, presentations	.docx .pptx	4355 KB 8.1 MB
4	Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems	Knowledge gaps related to indicators, data, methods and models used to monitor and assess bioeconomy.	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx .xlsx	500 KB
5	Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	Description of data needs and best methodologies on indicators for monitoring specific aspects of the sustainability transition in the case studies	Notes, spreadsheets, reports	.docx .xlsx	40 MB
6	Development of a framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition, including a dashboard for stakeholders	Data on indicators, data, methods and models used to monitor and assess bioeconomy	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx .xlsx	800 KB
7	Selection and definition of case studies from four	Report on selection steps and final selection including	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx .xlsx	10 MB

	critical sectors and case study analysis	fact sheets on short listed case studies. Also excels with long and short lists of potential case study candidates.	ts, reports		
8	Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations	Two reports with separate chapters per case study, reports on outcomes of workshops and several excel files with collected data, knowledge in a predefined structure	Notes, spreadsheets, reports	.docx .xlsx	80 MB
9	Development of policy portfolio scenarios will formulate scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, that will define the final input requirements	List of policy instruments and related case sector specific goals (e.g. amount of CO2 reduction, energy reduction, efficiency increase), Scenario description, Presentation in the Workshops	Spreadsheet, report, Presentation	.csv .docx pptx.	500KB
10	Model simulation and validation of the results	Output of macroeconomic, social and environmental key indicators, such as GDP, emissions, energy demand, employment and more	Spreadsheets, potentially diagrams, report.	.xlsx .docx	Size of output data is approx. 20-30MB per country model, for a total of about 100 Mb including simulations Size of report approx. 10-15MB
11	The development and calibration of the simulation model	System of National Accounts, macroeconomic data (population, employment, GDP, etc.), land use data, final energy consumption, power generation, GHG emissions, relevant statistics on bio-economy sectors, scenario	Spreadsheet	.xlsx	Input data: approx. 15-20MB
12	Capacity building for local stakeholders	Presentations, documentation of SUSTRACK tools/methods, capacity building materials from the model simulation, guidance for utilisation of all materials.	Text documents, presentations, recording videos.	.docx .pdf .pptx .mp4 (or similar)	500 KB
13	Identification of policy	Data in literature and	Text	.docx	2-10MB

	priorities	EU2020 at policy level.	documents , presentations	.xlsx .pptx	
14	Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy	data on prioritized policy actions at EU and CS level, presentations	Text documents , presentations	.docx .pdf .pptx	2-10 MB
15	Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK's Advisory Board	Information of candidate AB members (e.g., name and surname, mail, brief description of professional profile)	Notes, spreadsheets, images	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg	500 KB
16	Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences	Photos, number of event participants, presentations, interviews, surveys, Direct data input by users by newsletter subscription	Notes, spreadsheets, images, presentations	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .ppt, .jpeg, .png	1000 KB
17	Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities	Website and social media analytics, Data collected from project events, Newsletter subscriptions, Data collected from dissemination and communication activities/actions	Text document spreadsheets, presentations, audio-visual files, images	.docx .pdf .xlsx .csv .ppt .mp4 .jpeg .png	1000 KB

2.5 Data utility

The stakeholders who found meaningful utility in the data collected and generated by SUSTRACK—both within and beyond the consortium—together with the potential benefits arising from their use, are concisely summarised in the following table (Table 2):

Table 2: Data utility

Stakeholder group	Data utility
Policy makers	SUSTRACK aimed to support policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways for replacing fossil-based, carbon-intensive systems with circular, bio-based alternatives at both EU and regional levels. Throughout the project, the data collected and generated were used to produce guidelines, policy recommendations, and the identification of priority areas for intervention. As a result, these datasets proved to be of particular utility for experts responsible for designing, implementing, and funding relevant policies, providing them with robust, evidence-based insights to inform decision-making.
Industrial ecosystem	The data created and generated through SUSTRACK provided valuable insights into effective approaches for networking and

	<p>stakeholder engagement, helping to build the connections necessary to accelerate bio-based innovation. The project's results contributed to (i) raising awareness of bio-based systems and their benefits, and (ii) supplying evidence-based feedback at the policy level on how to integrate bio-based value chain development into broader policies and regional development plans. In this context, the datasets produced by SUSTRACK proved particularly useful for industry advisors and investors, supporting their engagement in the implementation and funding of initiatives aligned with sustainable and circular bio-based policies.</p>
Scientific community	<p>Within the SUSTRACK project, interdisciplinary research was carried out, building upon prior research efforts to generate new insights into the transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems across Europe. In parallel, local stakeholders were actively engaged in co-creation, mutual learning, and validation activities aimed at identifying the environmental, economic, and social limits of a carbon-intensive, fossil-based economy and at improving existing assessment methodologies. The research data generated through SUSTRACK were published in project reports and peer-reviewed scientific journals and were also deposited in open repositories. These datasets and publications are of high utility for the scientific community, as they aggregate and classify existing knowledge, while simultaneously creating new empirical open data to advance understanding of the transition to circular and bio-based systems.</p>
Civil society	<p>SUSTRACK actively engaged local stakeholders in its activities to ensure that their perspectives were considered in the development of regional policies.</p>
Project partners	<p>The data collected and generated during SUSTRACK formed the cornerstone for partners to produce evidence-based results and to achieve the project's objectives. These datasets enabled the co-creation and validation of findings that supported the integration of policy priorities into both regional and European agendas. Beyond the lifetime of the project, the data remain meaningful for consortium partners, allowing them to build on the knowledge created, explore new ideas, and capitalise on opportunities that can ensure the long-term sustainability and impact of SUSTRACK's results.</p>

3. FAIR DATA

The [Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template](#) emphasises the importance of ensuring that data produced by funded projects are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), thereby guaranteeing sound management and maximising impact. This requires the use of recognised standards and metadata to make data discoverable, clear procedures for data sharing and open access, the use of trusted repositories for long-term preservation, and practices that facilitate re-use by diverse stakeholders.

In line with these principles, SUSTRACK applied a structured methodology to make its datasets findable, accessible, and interoperable, while ensuring their preservation and open availability where appropriate. The following sections of this DMP describe how these FAIR principles were implemented in practice throughout the project, supporting transparency, long-term usability, and the widest possible re-use of the data generated.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Data discoverability and identification mechanism

SUSTRACK placed special emphasis on enhancing the discoverability of the data collected and generated throughout its activities. To this end, the project adopted a **metadata-driven approach** designed to improve the searchability of datasets while also facilitating their understanding and re-use. Metadata, defined as “data about data,” was systematically applied to describe the creation, content, and context of digital resources, whether individual files, parts of files, or collections. By using structured metadata, SUSTRACK ensured that datasets could be more easily discovered, managed, described, and preserved, while also strengthening relationships between digital resources⁹ and enabling their re-use across platforms and repositories.

In particular, three distinct types of metadata exist¹⁰, as presented below:

- **Descriptive metadata** is used to identify and describe collections and related information resources. Descriptive metadata at the local level helps with searching and retrieving. In an online environment, descriptive metadata helps to discover resources. Most of the time, it includes information such as the title, author, date, description, identifier, etc.
- **Administrative metadata** is used to facilitate the management of information resources. It is helpful for both short-term and long-term management and processing of data. This is information that will not usually be relevant to the public but will be essential for staff to manage collections internally. Such metadata may be location information, acquisition information, etc.
- **Structural metadata** enables the navigation and presentation of electronic resources. It documents how the components of an item are organized. Examples of structural metadata could be the way in which pages are ordered to form chapters of a book, a photograph that

⁹ Foulonneau, M., & Riley, J. (2008). Metadata for digital resources: Implementation, systems design and interoperability. Oxford: Chandos.

¹⁰ Caplan, P. (2003). Metadata fundamentals for all librarians. Chicago: American Library Association.

is included in a manuscript or a scrapbook or the JPEG and TIF files that were created from the original photograph negative, linked together.

With that in mind, data produced and used during SUSTRACK were made discoverable with metadata suitable to their content and format. The project employed metadata standards to produce rich and consistent records to support the long-term discovery, use, and integrity of its datasets (see Subsection 3.1.5 for further details on the metadata standards adopted by SUSTRACK).

In parallel, to further increase discoverability and accessibility, SUSTRACK deposited its open data into Zenodo, an open research data repository. A dedicated [SUSTRACK Zenodo community](#) was created to house all project outputs in one centralised and visible space, ensuring long-term preservation and easy access. Zenodo provides a trusted platform for publishing, finding, and re-using datasets, tools, and services for research, innovation, and educational purposes, under well-defined conditions that safeguard trust and public interest.

Using Zenodo, SUSTRACK achieved:

- seamless data access,
- effective implementation of FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) principles, and
- reliable re-use of research data and related digital objects produced across the project lifecycle (including methods and publications).
- Zenodo supports a broad range of file formats, promotes openly accessible peer-reviewed research, and allows the creation of dedicated collections. It was available to SUSTRACK free of charge for uploading and sharing data, as well as for external stakeholders to explore, download, and re-use outputs.

Figure 1 SUSTRACK Project Community profile on Zenodo

By using Zenodo, SUSTRACK ensured that uploaded datasets received globally resolvable Persistent Identifiers (DOIs), offering unique, permanent references to digital objects such as data records, documents, and visual resources.

As of October 2025, the SUSTRACK Zenodo community hosts 21 public records. Across these records, the cumulative usage statistics amount to 442 views and 419 downloads, demonstrating active interest and re-use potential of SUSTRACK's outputs.

Datasets that were not suitable for upload to Zenodo were stored in the project's secure cloud repository, with careful application of identification mechanisms and standard naming conventions. This ensured internal consistency, traceability, and ease of discovery by consortium partners even for files outside the public repository.

3.1.2 Naming conventions

Following a consistent set of naming conventions in the development of the project's data files greatly enhanced their searchability. To this end, SUSTRACK adopted clear and standardised file naming practices that provided immediate clues about the content, status, and version of each file, thereby improving their discoverability. By applying these conventions, project partners—as well as external stakeholders accessing open datasets—were able to easily identify, classify, and sort files, ensuring greater efficiency in collaboration and long-term data management.

According to the UK Data Archive ([UK Data Service, 2017b](#)), a best practice in naming convention is to create brief yet meaningful names for data files, that facilitate classification. The naming convention should avoid the utilisation of spaces, dots and special characters (such as & or!), whereas the use of underscores is endorsed, to separate elements in the data file name and make them understandable. At the same time, versioning should be a part of a naming convention to clearly identify the changes and edits in a file.

To facilitate consistent referencing of datasets produced during its implementation, SUSTRACK employed a standard naming convention that integrated versioning and accounted for the possibility of generating multiple datasets within a single activity. This approach ensured that each dataset could be uniquely identified, even when several were created under the same task or activity.

The naming convention incorporated a unique element to distinguish datasets produced within the same activity, thereby avoiding confusion and supporting traceability. In line with best practices, file names avoided spaces or special characters and used only the standard alphanumeric alphabet (A-Z, 0-9). This ensured compatibility across systems, improved interoperability, and simplified both internal and external use of SUSTRACK data.

[Name of project] _ [Name of Study] _ [Number of dataset] _ [Issue Date] _ [Version number]

- **Name of project:** SUSTRACK
- **Name of Study:** A short version of the name of the activity for which the dataset is created.
- **Number of dataset:** An indication of the number assigned to the dataset.
- **Issue Date:** The date on which the latest version of the dataset was modified (YYYY.MM.DD.).

- **Version number:** The versioning number of a dataset.

With the above in mind, some **indicative examples** to showcase the naming structure applied in the context of SUSTRACK are provided below:

- **SUSTRACK_Casestudies_Dataset1_2023.1.30_v1** -The first dataset generated from the collection of case studies from four critical sectors. In this task, cases are selected from four sectors that have been identified as facing critical challenges within the current linear system: (a) the construction sector; (b) the textile sector; (c) the (fine) chemical; and (d) the plastic sector. This is the first version of the dataset that was last modified on the 30th of January 2023.
- **SUSTRACK_GapAnalysis_Dataset1_2023.02.15_v1** -The first dataset generated from the gap analysis after the literature review. In this task, the environmental, economic, and social limits of the linear, carbon-intensive, and fossil-based economy have been identified. This is the first version of the dataset that was last modified on the 15th of February 2023.
- **SUSTRACK_KnowledgeGaps1_2023.02.27_V1.xlsx**. -The first dataset generated from the T2.1, identifying the body of knowledge. In this task, Next, the research items will be reviewed to identify gaps. This is the first version of the dataset that was last modified on the 27th of February 2023.

3.1.3 Search keywords

The project's data were enriched with search keywords to optimise their re-use by interested stakeholders throughout the project's lifetime and beyond. The metadata standards employed by SUSTRACK provided opportunities for tagging datasets and their content with meaningful keywords. As a subset of metadata, these keywords consisted of words and phrases used to classify and describe the data. Within SUSTRACK, keywords were systematically applied to add contextual information to the datasets, thereby facilitating their description, interpretation, discoverability, and overall value for re-use.

Along these lines, the project's strategy on keywords is underpinned by the following principles:

- The who, the what, the when, the where, and the why should be covered.
- Consistency among the different keyword tags needs to be ensured.
- Relevant, understandable and clear keywording ought to be sought.

In general, the keywords applied to SUSTRACK datasets comprised terms related to the **circular bioeconomy, governance models, and regional authorities**. The keywords were carefully selected to accurately reflect the content of each dataset, while avoiding terms that appeared only once or twice, thereby ensuring relevance, consistency, and effective discoverability.

3.1.4 Versioning

Versioning of information ensured that revisions of datasets were uniquely identifiable and that changes over time could be clearly traced. This practice enabled project partners to determine whether newer versions of a dataset were available, to understand the differences between versions, and to conduct comparisons without confusion. To support this process, a clear **version number indicator** was systematically included in the naming convention of every data file produced during SUSTRACK. This approach facilitated the accurate identification of dataset versions, improved transparency, and safeguarded the integrity of project outputs.

3.1.5 Standards for metadata creation

SUSTRACK applied recognised standards for creating metadata for all data collected and generated by the project, with the aim of producing rich descriptions that improved discoverability, searchability, and re-use. This approach enabled effective searching, enhanced digital curation, and facilitated data sharing. In addition, the metadata standards used supported the integration of metadata from a variety of sources into other technical systems.

For SUSTRACK's openly available data, the metadata standards provided by Zenodo were applied. Zenodo automatically generates metadata for uploaded datasets, extending their reach to a wide audience of interested stakeholders. These metadata records can be exported in several open and machine-readable formats, including MARCXML, Dublin Core, and the DataCite Metadata Schema, ensuring broad interoperability and long-term preservation.

Project data not immediately available for re-use were also annotated with open and machine-readable metadata following the [Dublin Core Metadata standard](#) (ISO 15836). Dublin Core was selected for its simplicity, wide recognition, and compatibility with Zenodo. This ensured that any datasets initially closed but potentially made open at a later stage (e.g. due to revised consortium policies) retained valid and interoperable metadata.

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 Openly available and closed data

SUSTRACK followed the guidelines of the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template and adhered to the FAIR principles and the rule of being “as open as possible, as closed as necessary.” The project aimed to make the data collected and generated openly available with minimal restrictions, while at the same time ensuring the protection of sensitive information from inappropriate access. This required project partners to disseminate datasets that could provide long-term value to external stakeholders, without compromising the confidentiality or privacy of the individuals and organisations that contributed to data collection.

In line with this approach, only anonymised and aggregated data were made openly available to ensure that data subjects could not be identified in reports, publications, or datasets resulting from SUSTRACK. The partner responsible for each dataset undertook the necessary anonymisation procedures, ensuring that information was processed in such a way that the data subject was no longer identifiable (see Chapter 6 for further details on responsibilities).

During anonymisation, direct and indirect identifiers were removed, generalised, aggregated, or distorted as appropriate. It is important to distinguish anonymisation from pseudonymisation, as defined under the GDPR: while anonymisation irreversibly prevents the re-identification of data subjects, pseudonymisation allows for re-identification if additional information is made available. SUSTRACK therefore applied anonymisation wherever open dissemination was foreseen, ensuring GDPR compliance and safeguarding stakeholder trust.

To support this process, the consortium drew on established good practices for anonymising quantitative and qualitative data, as recommended in the tour guide on data management of the **Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)**. A detailed overview of these practices is presented in the following table (Table 3).

Table 3: Good practices for data anonymisation

Type of data	Good practices
Quantitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Remove or aggregate variables or reduce the precision or detailed textual meaning of a variable. ● Aggregate or reduce the precision of a variable such as age or place of residence. As a general rule, report the lowest level of geo-referencing that will not potentially breach respondent confidentiality. ● Generalise the meaning of a detailed text variable by replacing potentially disclosive free-text responses with more general text. ● Restrict the upper or lower ranges of a continuous variable to hide outliers if the values for certain individuals are unusual or atypical within the wider group researched.
Qualitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use pseudonyms or generic descriptors to edit identifying information, rather than blanking-out that information. ● Plan anonymisation at the time of transcription or initial write-up, (longitudinal studies may be an exception if relationships between waves of interviews need special attention for harmonised editing). ● Use pseudonyms or replacements that are consistent within the research team and throughout the project. For example, using the same pseudonyms in publications and follow-up research. ● Use 'search and replace' techniques carefully so that unintended changes are not made, and misspelt words are not missed. ● Identify replacements in the text clearly, for example with [brackets] or using XML tags such as <seg> word to be anonymised</seg>. <p>Create an anonymisation log (also known as a de-anonymisation key) of all replacements, aggregations or removals made and store such a log securely and separately from the anonymised data files.</p>

Source: Tour guide on data management of the CESSDA¹¹

It is important to note that all personal data collected during the project were initially treated as **closed data**. Only after undergoing anonymisation and aggregation were they considered eligible for open sharing, thereby safeguarding the confidentiality and privacy of the data subjects.

3.2.2 Data accessibility and availability

Public access to SUSTRACK's open data was ensured through Zenodo, where datasets were deposited and made fully accessible with rich metadata and search functionality. This guaranteed long-term visibility, interoperability, and discoverability of the project's outputs. At the same time, closed data were securely stored and shared only among authorised members of the consortium using cloud storage and file-sharing services (e.g. Google Drive). Before adopting these services—whether provided within or outside the EEA—the consortium verified their compliance with the relevant GDPR requirements.

The following table (Table 4) presents an overview of where SUSTRACK data were made accessible.

Table 4: Data accessibility

No	Data	Accessibility
1	Gap analysis	The results were shared in D1.1 (M6) which is a public report.
2	Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy	The results were shared in D1.2 (M15) which is a public report
3	Prioritising identified limits	The results were shared in D1.3 (M18) which is a public report
4	Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems	The results were shared in D2.1 which is a public report
5	Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	The results were shared in 2 reports, D2.2 and D2.3 which are both public reports
6	Development of a framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition	The results were shared in D2.4 which is a public report. In addition, the SUSTRACK monitoring tool will be openly accessible through the SUSTRACK website.
7	Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis	The results were shared in D3.1 which is a public report.
8	Analysis of findings and derivation of main	The results were shared in 2 reports,

¹¹ Retrieved from: <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/5.-Protect/Anonymisation>

	conclusions and recommendations from the case studies	Deliverable 3.3 and 3.4 which are both public reports
9	Development of policy portfolio scenarios will formulate scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, which will define the final input requirements	The results were shared in D4.1, as a public report
10	Model simulation and validation of the results	Documentation of data sources were provided within deliverable D4.2, which is a public report
11	Capacity building for local stakeholders Results of the activities will be reported in D5.4, as a public report. Additionally, other capacity-building materials will be made available as presentations, documentation or videos on the SUSTRACK website and during stakeholder engagement activities.	Results of the activities were reported in D5.4, as a public report. Additionally, other capacity-building materials were made available as presentations, documentation or videos on the SUSTRACK website and during stakeholder engagement activities.
12	Identification of policy priorities	Results of the activities have been reported in the public deliverable D5.1.
13	Policy options, challenges and stakeholder recommendations on sector- and country-specific policy needs	Results are available in D5.3 (public report).
14	Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy results will be made available in D5.5 as a public report.	Results made available in D5.2 and D5.5 (public reports).
15	Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK's Advisory Board	Data were stored in a consortium cloud server.
16	Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences	Data were stored in a consortium cloud server.
17	Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities	Data were stored in a consortium cloud server and will be used to fill the communication and dissemination templates on the EC participant portal. Activities are also be reported in D6.2 and D6.5.
18	Website and social media analytics	Quantitative data from website and social media analytics are anonymous and were shared with the consortium, the EU Commission. These data are reported in D6.2 and D6.5
19	Data collected from project events	Data collected from project events were shared with the consortium, the EU Commission and the participants of the event upon the sign of a consent form.
20	Newsletter subscription	Data were collected in a dedicated cloud server owned by FVA

		(communication and dissemination leader) in Hostinger. The data were only used by the communications manager of the project, and it were not shared with anyone else. Quantitative data were extracted from it to share the analytics with the project partners, as well as in D6.2 and D6.5. Permission to manage the data was provided at the time of collecting it.
21	The development and calibration of the simulation model	A documentation of data sources was provided within deliverable D4.2, which is a public report.

Explanation of Dataset References

The data listed in Table 4 correspond to the structured data collections generated and used within the SUSTRACK project activities. While Table 4 summarises accessibility in relation to public deliverables, a consolidated and detailed description of all datasets – including their type, storage location, accessibility level, FAIR status, and justification for confidentiality where applicable – is provided in Annex IV (Dataset Inventory) of this DMP. “Model simulation and validation of the results” and “Development and calibration of the simulation model” are merged into “GEM Model Input Data” in Annex IV.

3.2.3 Methods, software tools and documentation to access the data

SUSTRACK placed strong emphasis on ensuring the accessibility of all data collected and generated during the project. No specialised methods, software tools, or additional documentation were required to access the open datasets. Stakeholders were able to access the data simply by using a standard web browser (e.g. Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome, Safari, Microsoft Edge) on a computer, smartphone, or tablet.

More specifically, users could access the project’s datasets directly via the [SUSTRACK Zenodo community](#). By entering the project name or relevant keywords into the Zenodo search engine, users were directed to SUSTRACK’s openly available datasets, which were ready for exploration and re-use. Since the data were deposited in open and widely supported formats, they could be appropriately read and processed by a broad range of commonly available software applications, ensuring usability across different stakeholder groups.

Closed data, by contrast, were accessible only to authorised project partners. These were stored and managed through the consortium’s secure cloud storage services. As with the open datasets, no specialised tools or methods were required to access these files beyond standard login credentials.

3.2.4 Data, metadata, and data integrity

SUSTRACK's open data, together with their associated metadata, and any relevant code or documentation required for access and re-use, were deposited in and securely stored by Zenodo. While it is highly unlikely that Zenodo will discontinue its operations, contingency measures were considered: in the event of such a scenario, all data, metadata, and documentation uploaded by SUSTRACK would be transferred without undue delay to another trusted open-access repository. Importantly, because all openly available SUSTRACK datasets were assigned Persistent Identifiers (PIDs/DOIs), links to the data would remain valid and unaffected by any repository migration.

In parallel, project data not intended for open access were stored—together with their accompanying metadata, and documentation where applicable—in the secure cloud-based storage service used by the consortium. This ensured that both open and closed data remained safely preserved, accessible to the appropriate audiences, and compliant with FAIR and GDPR principles.

3.2.5 Restrictions

By utilising Zenodo for sharing its openly available data, SUSTRACK was able to apply different levels of accessibility, taking into account ethical, legal, and practical considerations (including personal data protection, intellectual property, commercial sensitivities, privacy, and security).

Zenodo provided the following levels of data accessibility:

- **Open access:** Data remains openly available for re-use, with the scope and conditions of re-use determined by the licence assigned to each dataset (see Subsection 3.4.1).
- **Embargoed access:** Data remains restricted until the end of a defined embargo period, after which they automatically became publicly accessible.
- **Restricted access:** Data that is not publicly available; access is granted only with the approval of the responsible project partner.
- **Closed access:** Data is protected from all external access and could only be used internally by SUSTRACK consortium members.

Project partners primarily used the open access level to disseminate data of long-term value to stakeholders and ensured open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications produced in the project, in line with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. Specifically, the consortium guaranteed that:

- At the latest upon publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript was deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- Immediate open access was provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the most recent version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or an equivalent licence. For monographs and other long-text formats, licences could exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND).
- Information was provided, via the repository, on any research outputs, tools, or instruments necessary to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.
- Beneficiaries (or authors) retained sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with these open access obligations.

- In accordance with the FAIR principles, metadata of deposited publications were made openly available under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or an equivalent licence. Metadata included at minimum: author(s), title, publication date, venue, Horizon Europe grant details (project name, acronym, and number), licensing terms, and persistent identifiers (for publications, authors, organisations, and, where applicable, related research outputs or tools).

Through this approach, SUSTRACK ensured that its data were as openly accessible as possible, while safeguarding sensitive information and complying with legal and ethical requirements. In this context, the project also prioritised the use of metadata standards and vocabularies to enhance interoperability, as described in the following section.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data interoperability refers to the ability of systems and services that create, exchange, and use data to share clear and common expectations regarding the content, context, and meaning of that data¹². In line with this principle, SUSTRACK incorporated the use of recognised metadata vocabularies, standards, and methods into its data management methodology to maximise the interoperability of the data collected and generated during the project.

For datasets not publicly shared, interoperability was ensured through the use of the Dublin Core Metadata standard¹³. This standard provides a concise yet effective “metadata element set” that supports quality, consistency, and broad compatibility with other data sources in the linked data environment. The Dublin Core’s fifteen core elements—such as title, creator, subject, and date—offered a controlled vocabulary with natural-language definitions that could be directly expressed in open, machine-readable formats (e.g. XML, HTML). This machine-processability facilitated automatic discovery, exchange, and integration of SUSTRACK’s metadata across platforms and repositories.

Each element of the Dublin Core standard is optional and repeatable, and the framework supports refinement through encoding schemes and controlled vocabularies. By adopting this standard, SUSTRACK ensured that its metadata could be consistently understood by both humans and machines, thereby enhancing the re-usability of its outputs and safeguarding their long-term value.

The following table (Table 5) presents the Dublin Core vocabulary elements applied in SUSTRACK.

¹² L. Steele & T. Orrell (2017). The frontiers of data interoperability for sustainable development. Publish What You Fund and Development Initiatives

¹³ Sugimoto, S., Baker, T., & Weibel, S. L. (2002). Dublin Core: Process and Principles. Lecture Notes in Computer Science Digital Libraries: People, Knowledge, and Technology, 25-35.

Table 5: Dublin Core Metadata standard vocabulary

No	Element	Element definition
1	Title	A name given to the resource.
2	Creator	An entity primarily responsible for making the content of the resource.
3	Subject	The topic of the content of the resource.
4	Description	An account of the content of the resource.
5	Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available.
6	Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource.
7	Date	A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource
8	Type	The nature or genre of the content of the resource.
9	Format	The physical or digital manifestation of the resource.
10	Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
11	Source	A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.
12	Language	A language of the intellectual content of the resource.
13	Relation	A reference to a related resource.
14	Coverage	The extent or scope of the content of the resource.
15	Rights	Information about rights held in and over the resource.

Similarly, the interoperability of SUSTRACK's openly available data was facilitated through Zenodo, where metadata were stored internally in JSON format according to a defined JSON schema. This schema included HTML microdata, enabling machine-readable data to be embedded

within HTML documents in the form of nested name-value pairs. In addition, the JSON schema provided a collection of shared vocabularies in microdata format, allowing datasets to be marked up in a way that could be consistently interpreted by major search engines.

Furthermore, all metadata associated with SUSTRACK's open datasets were made available via the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH), enabling external systems to harvest and index them. The OAI-PMH framework promotes interoperability by supporting efficient metadata dissemination across diverse communities and repositories¹⁴. By leveraging these standards and protocols, SUSTRACK ensured that its open data were not only discoverable but also seamlessly integrated into the broader ecosystem of linked and reusable research outputs.

3.4 Increase data re-use

3.4.1 License schemes to permit the widest use possible

The application of a licence to SUSTRACK's open data was a straightforward way to ensure that interested third parties could re-use the datasets under clearly defined conditions. Licences function as instruments that permit third parties to copy, distribute, display, and/or modify project data, but only for the purposes permitted by the licence terms. While specific terms vary, three conditions are commonly included: attribution, non-derivative use, and non-commerciality.

In line with FAIR principles and Horizon Europe requirements, SUSTRACK published its openly available data under the Creative Commons licensing scheme, thereby fostering re-use and supporting an equitable, transparent, and accessible environment.

Through its dedicated community, Zenodo provided SUSTRACK with the opportunity to apply Creative Commons licences to all open datasets. In practice, SUSTRACK provided the use of five key Creative Commons licence options, namely:

- Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 (CC BY-SA 4.0) according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, must be distributed under the same license as the original. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

Figure 2: CC BY-SA 4.0

Figure 3: CC BY 4.0

¹⁴ Corrado, E.M. (2005) 'The importance of open access, open source, and open standards for libraries', Issues in Science and Technology Librarianship.

- Creative Commons Attribution-No Derivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-ND 4.0) during which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however, must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0) based on which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get permission from project partners first. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0) according to which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get permission from project partners first. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however, must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

Figure 4: CC BY-ND 4.0

Figure 5: CC BY-NC 4.0

Figure 6: CC BY-NC-ND

3.4.2 Availability for re-use

The re-use of data was a central component of SUSTRACK’s approach to making data FAIR. By ensuring that datasets were made available for re-use, the project enabled stakeholders beyond the consortium to benefit from its results, thereby maximising impact and supporting broader scientific, policy, and industry communities. Rich metadata—created in line with recognised standards—together with appropriate licensing schemes, further facilitated discovery and ensured that SUSTRACK’s open data could be re-used effectively and responsibly.

In principle, datasets were made available for re-use no later than 120 days after the completion of their processing (e.g. collection, anonymisation, aggregation). This ensured that the necessary data management procedures could be finalised without delaying the timely delivery of the project’s planned outputs.

With this in mind, the timeframe for making SUSTRACK datasets openly accessible and uploading them to Zenodo is provided in the following table (Table 6).

Table 6: Expected time that data will be made open through Zenodo

No	Data	Expected time for making data open	Notes
1	Gap analysis	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18)
2	Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18)

	the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy		
3	Prioritising identified limits	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18)
4	Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems	2023	None
5	Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	31/10/2025	After the final report (M36)
6	Development of a framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition	31/10/2025	After the final report (M36)
7	Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18)
8	Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations	31/10/2025	After the final report (M36)
9	Development of policy portfolio scenarios will formulate scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, that will define the final input requirements	31/01/2024	None
10	Model simulation and validation of the results	01/05/2025	Organizing online webinars (involving at least 20 stakeholders, each) to transfer knowledge and support further applications of the model
11	Capacity building for local stakeholders	31/07/2025	None
12	Identification of policy priorities	31/12/2023	None
13	Policy options, challenges and stakeholder recommendations on sector- and country-specific policy needs	31/10/2025	After the final report (M36)

13	Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy	31/10/2025	After the final report (M36)
15	Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)
16	Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)
17	Website and social media analytics	30/04/2024-31/10/2025	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)
18	Data collected from project events	30/04/2024-31/10/2025	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)
19	Newsletter subscription	30/04/2024-31/10/2025	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)
20	Data collected from dissemination and communication actions	30/04/2024-31/10/2025	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)

4. DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE

Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) formed an integral part of SUSTRACK's data management methodology and were systematically applied before publishing any datasets on Zenodo. These measures ensured the transparency, consistency, comparability, completeness, and accuracy of the project's data.

QA consisted of planned review procedures carried out independently of dataset development, by personnel not directly involved in data compilation. Within SUSTRACK, this included peer reviews of methods and data summaries to verify scientific soundness, highlight areas for improvement, and ensure that datasets accurately reflected the evidence produced.

QC referred to operational checks performed throughout dataset development to maintain quality. These involved routine technical verifications to assess consistency, correctness, integrity, and completeness, as well as the identification and correction of errors or omissions. QC procedures covered all phases of the data lifecycle, from acquisition and handling to the application of approved methodologies and documentation practices.

Typical QC checks included:

- identifying transcription errors in data entry,
- confirming that scale measures fell within acceptable ranges, and
- verifying compliance with the project's naming conventions.

By combining QA and QC processes, SUSTRACK ensured that its datasets met high scientific and technical standards, reinforcing their reliability and maximising their value for re-use.

5. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

5.1 KE Srl Green Economy Model (GEM)

For the SUSTRACK project, the Green Economy Model (GEM) was used and further enhanced to include bio-based dynamics required for analysing the selected case study sectors. The software applied for the development and parameterisation of the model was Vensim DSS. GEM was employed to analyse the systemic impacts of transitioning towards a more bio-based economy, drawing on case study inputs and the formulation of transition scenarios.

A baseline simulation and multiple transition scenarios were conducted to enable a comparative assessment of impacts across socioeconomic and environmental performance indicators. GEM was informed primarily by the case study analyses carried out under WP3 and the scenarios defined in WP4 (Task 4.1), while also incorporating relevant knowledge and data generated in WP1 and WP2 to ensure accurate representation of sectoral and macroeconomic dynamics linked to the bio-based economy.

The cross-sectoral analysis of policy impacts involved simulating scenarios up to 2050 to examine how the system performed under different policy conditions supporting the transition to a bio-based economy. By comparing transition scenarios against the baseline, the consortium assessed the economy-wide benefits and drawbacks of policy interventions. GEM produced forecasts for macroeconomic indicators such as GDP, employment, and emissions, estimated the additional investments required to enable the transition, and quantified and monetised related externalities. This facilitated the development of a system-wide cost-benefit analysis, integrating additional investments, avoided costs, and resulting benefits within a single analytical framework.

Stakeholders involved in and benefitting from the GEM included both project partners and external audiences such as policymakers, academic institutions, and professional networks. Within the consortium, WP5 partners contributed to identifying policy priorities and defining policy actions. External stakeholders used the model's insights and datasets to inform policy development and research in their respective domains.

The data generated by GEM included model files (.mdl, approximately 5 MB), simulation output files (.vdf, approximately 800 MB per simulation), and Excel output datasets (.xlsx, approximately 1-5 MB each). These data were stored offline in structured Excel spreadsheets and, where appropriate, shared via secure cloud platforms such as Google Drive or Dropbox.

The model, its documentation, and the simulation outputs were made publicly available through project deliverables under Tasks 4.2 and 4.3, ensuring open access to the results once the scenarios were fully simulated and validated with project partners and stakeholders.

The FAIR management principles defined in Section 3 of this DMP guided the handling of these research outputs, ensuring that all data were findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, thereby promoting transparency, collaboration, and long-term reusability of SUSTRACK's modelling results.

6. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

6.1 Estimated costs for making data FAIR

The costs required for making the data collected and generated during SUSTRACK's activities compliant with the FAIR principles were integrated into the project's budget. To produce these estimations, the consortium relied on assumptions informed by the guidelines of the Research Data Management Support network of Utrecht University¹⁵ and the UK Data Service Data Management Costing Tool¹⁶. Accordingly, the estimated costs covered activities and resources across the entire data lifecycle, from collection and documentation through storage and preservation, to sharing and re-use.

Data collection costs covered activities related to gathering and generating new data, transcribing (if applicable), formatting and organising files, and obtaining informed consent from data subjects. As SUSTRACK primarily relied on newly collected/generated data, this category represented the largest share of the FAIR-related costs.

Data documentation costs included the effort required to describe datasets (e.g. variable and value labels) and to create rich metadata with contextual and methodological details explaining how data were collected, generated, and processed.

Data storage costs were minimal, as adequate storage space was already available to partners and no additional infrastructure was required. These costs were mainly linked to ensuring data back-ups.

Data access and security costs were also modest, since access control and protection were inherently provided by the repositories and secure cloud services used by SUSTRACK. No special software or additional measures were required.

Overall data management costs covered the operationalisation of data management activities throughout the project, including coordination, monitoring, and compliance with FAIR requirements.

Long-term preservation costs were negligible, as SUSTRACK's open data were deposited in Zenodo free of charge, where they will remain accessible with persistent identifiers (DOIs).

6.2 Data management responsibilities

For the effective, proper, and secure handling of data collected and generated during SUSTRACK, specific data management roles and responsibilities were established within the project's methodology and procedures. These are outlined below:

Project Coordinator (UNIT): UNIT was responsible for overall data management in SUSTRACK, PEDAL was in charge for the elaboration and updating of the Data Management Plan (DMP) with

¹⁵ Research Data Management Support. Guides: Costs of data management. Utrecht University. Retrieved from: <https://www.uu.nl/en/research/research-data-management/guides/costs-of-data-management>

¹⁶ UK Data Service. Costing Data Management. Retrieved from: <https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/plan/costing>

support from all partners. PEDAL prepared templates for the Informed Consent Form and the Data Subject Request Form, ensuring that partners could adapt them to their activities, and drafted the project’s Privacy Policy (published on the project website). In collaboration with relevant Task Leaders, UNIT reviewed whether specific privacy policies were required for individual project tasks and coordinated their development. PEDAL also worked closely with Work Package Leaders (WPLs), Task Leaders (TLs), and Responsible Partners to determine whether and how data would be shared or re-used, contributed to quality assurance, and managed the uploading of SUSTRACK’s openly available data to Zenodo.

Work Package Leaders (WPLs): WPLs coordinated data processing activities within their WPs. They aligned with PEDAL and TLs to decide on data sharing and re-use procedures, including access levels, embargo periods, and any required software or tools. WPLs were also responsible for the quality of data produced within their WP, assessing dataset integrity and identifying improvements in collaboration with TLs.

Task Leaders (TLs): TLs oversaw the collection and generation of data within their tasks and ensured timely and appropriate processing. They were responsible for adapting consent and request form templates to their activities, identifying whether a specific privacy policy was needed, and collaborating with UNIT for drafting and release. TLs also prepared datasets for sharing—either within the consortium or publicly—by applying naming conventions, anonymisation techniques, and appropriate metadata and documentation.

Partners: All partners were responsible for collecting, digitising, anonymising, storing, destroying, and otherwise processing data relevant to their activities. They ensured that consent was appropriately obtained, using forms adapted to the project’s Privacy Policy, relevant task-specific policies, and their organisation’s national legal context. Partners managed collected consent forms to demonstrate compliance with EU and national regulations. They also performed quality checks to maintain dataset integrity.

The following table (Table 7) illustrates the allocation of data management responsibilities among SUSTRACK partners for datasets collected and generated under each Work Package.

Table 7: Data management responsibilities of SUSTRACK’s partners per data collected/generated under each WP

WP	WPL	Data	Task	WTL	Responsible partners
WP1	UNIT	Gap analysis	T1.1	UNIT	KE, UNIFE, BAM, TECNALIA, UGENT
		Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy	T1.2	BAM	UNIT, TECNALIA, UNIFE, PC, KE, FVA
		Co-creation focus group	T1.2.1	PEDAL	UNIT, TECNALIA, UNIFE, PC, KE, FVA
		Interviews and surveys	T1.2.2	BAM	UNIT, TECNALIA, UNIFE, PC, KE, FVA
		Prioritising identified limits	T1.3	UNIT	CIRCE, BAM, TECNALIA, UNIFE, PC, DBFZ, KE, WR

WP2	TECNALIA	Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems	T2.1	TECNALIA	DBFZ, KE, BAM, UNIFE, UNIT, WR, FVA, UGENT
		Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	T2.2	WR	CIRCE, FVA, DBFZ, KE, TECNALIA, UNIT
		Development of a framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition	T2.3	TECNALIA	FVA, DBFZ, BAM, UNIT, WR, KE, PEDAL
WP3	WR	Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis	T3.1	BAM	All Partners
		Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations from the case studies	T3.4	WR	UGENT, UNIT, CIRCE, PC, KE, TECNALIA, DBFZ, BAM
WP4	KE	Development of policy portfolio scenarios will formulate scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, that will define the final input requirements	T4.1	DBFZ	UNIT, BAM, WR, TECNALIA, KE, UNIFE, PC, UGENT
		Model simulation and validation of the results	T4.2	KE	WR, TECNALIA, BAM, FVA
WP5	DBFZ	Capacity building for local stakeholders	T5.2	DBFZ	All Partners
		Identification of policy priorities	T5.1	WR	UNIT, DBFZ, CIRCE, PC, FVA, KE, BAM, TECNALIA
		Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy	T5.3	DBFZ	UNIT, WR, BAM, TECNALIA, PC, FVA, KE
WP6	FVA	Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK's Advisory Board	T6.2	PC	All partners
		Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences	T6.2	PC	All Partners
		Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities	T6.1	FVA	All Partners

7. DATA SECURITY

SUSTRACK securely handled all data collected and generated throughout its lifecycle, recognising the importance of safeguarding these data against accidental loss and unauthorised access. Appropriate technical and organisational measures were applied, based on risk assessments that considered both the impact and likelihood of potential data breaches. The project's data security strategy aimed to minimise the probability of breaches during and after the project, whether arising from human error, hardware failure, or malicious activity, and to prevent unauthorised access. Particular emphasis was placed on ensuring that any personal data collected could only be accessed by authorised personnel. In cases of unauthorised access or stolen data, the provisions of the Grant Agreement were followed.

All consortium partners accepted responsibility for processing data¹⁷ using secure infrastructures such as private servers or cloud services compliant with relevant data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR). These safeguards ensured that closed data, which were not intended for sharing or re-use, were adequately protected. Regular integrity checks¹⁸ were conducted to verify that stored data remained unchanged and uncorrupted.

Access to closed data was strictly limited to authorised partners. In the event of a personal data breach, the responsible partner was required to notify its competent national supervisory authority (e.g., national Data Protection Authority) and the affected data subject(s) without undue delay, and no later than 72 hours after becoming aware of the breach. Breach documentation included details of the incident, its impact, and remedial actions taken. There was no incident to be reported.

Identification and authentication controls were applied throughout SUSTRACK. Each partner was responsible for implementing appropriate access controls for the data under their remit. The SUSTRACK website also incorporated technical access controls, defining role-based access rights so that only authorised personnel could reach specific datasets. Individual accounts, protected by username and password authentication, were issued to responsible partners, ensuring accountability and traceability. Dedicated privacy policies governed the SUSTRACK website, describing how personal data were collected, processed, and used; the security procedures in place; users' rights; and the cookies policy.

In terms of open data, SUSTRACK relied on Zenodo for long-term preservation. Both datasets and their associated metadata were securely stored, with replication across multiple servers ensuring redundancy and recovery in case of data loss. Zenodo also applied checks validation (MD5) to detect and prevent file corruption. Access control was managed through Zenodo's defined levels of openness (open, embargoed, restricted, closed), aligning with project and ethical requirements.

¹⁷ Processing, according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation), means any operation or set of operations which are performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

¹⁸ An integrity check is the process of comparing the current state of stored data and/or programs to a previously recorded state in order to detect any changes.

8. ETHICS AND OTHER ISSUES

This chapter addressed the ethical considerations of SUSTRACK's DMP and ensured compliance of all data collected and generated under the project. SUSTRACK only processed non-sensitive personal data, meaning data not included in any special categories under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

In line with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), all personal data processed during SUSTRACK's activities were:

- processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently;
- collected for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes linked to the project's objectives;
- adequate, relevant, and limited to what was necessary;
- accurate and, where required, kept up to date;
- stored in a form permitting identification of data subjects for no longer than necessary;
- protected with appropriate technical and organisational security measures (see Section 7).

For every personal data processing activity, at least one lawful basis under Article 6 GDPR applied. Where informed consent served as the lawful basis, all provisions of Article 7 GDPR were strictly observed. The project developed and applied a Privacy Policy, alongside standard templates for the Informed Consent Form and the Data Subject Request Form, all compliant with GDPR. These templates were annexed to the DMP (Annex I, Annex II and Annex III).

No transfers of personal data outside the EU took place during SUSTRACK. Where data storage providers were used, whether inside or outside the EEA, partners ensured their compliance with GDPR requirements before use.

Each partner was responsible for adapting the standard templates to (i) the specific needs of the activity and (ii) the relevant national or organisational data protection regulations. Partners also accepted responsibility for retaining appropriate records of consent, ensuring transparency and accountability, and for enabling simple mechanisms for data subjects to withdraw consent at any time.

Finally, it should be noted that no additional national, funder, sectoral, or departmental procedures for data management were required or applied within SUSTRACK beyond GDPR compliance and the measures outlined in this DMP.

9. CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD

The SUSTRACK Data Management Plan (DMP) provided a consolidated framework to ensure that all data collected, generated, and processed during the project was managed in compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable), the Horizon Europe requirements, and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Throughout its implementation, the consortium applied consistent standards and procedures to ensure transparency, security, interoperability, and long-term preservation of project data. Particular emphasis was placed on safeguarding personal data, promoting open access wherever possible, and enabling effective re-use of results by policymakers, researchers, industry, and civil society.

The establishment of clear roles and responsibilities, together with quality assurance and quality control mechanisms, ensured that SUSTRACK's data management processes were both reliable and sustainable. By depositing openly available datasets in the dedicated SUSTRACK Zenodo community, the project created a central repository for its outputs, equipped with persistent identifiers (DOIs), rich metadata, and open licensing conditions. This guarantees the long-term discoverability, accessibility, and usability of the data beyond the lifetime of the project.

Looking forward, the SUSTRACK DMP will serve as a legacy instrument for the consortium and broader stakeholder community. While no further updates are foreseen after the conclusion of the project, the structures put in place—including metadata standards, anonymisation practices, and storage strategies—can continue to guide partners in future research and innovation activities. The availability of SUSTRACK's open data on Zenodo provides a foundation for further research, policy development, and cross-project synergies in the field of circular and bio-based systems.

Reflections and Lessons Learned

The implementation of the DMP during SUSTRACK also generated valuable lessons for future projects. The importance of consistent metadata application emerged as a key enabler of data discoverability and re-use, underscoring the need for early and continuous attention to metadata quality. The anonymisation of personal data proved essential but at times challenging, requiring careful balancing of compliance with GDPR and maintaining data utility. The use of a dedicated Zenodo community demonstrated clear benefits, providing both visibility and credibility for SUSTRACK's outputs, while ensuring their integration into a broader European open science ecosystem. Finally, the experience highlighted the added value of embedding data management practices into everyday project workflows rather than treating them as an isolated compliance requirement.

By capturing these lessons, SUSTRACK not only ensured the long-term accessibility of its results but also contributed to strengthening best practices for data management in Horizon Europe and beyond.

ANNEXES

Annex I Privacy Policy

Within this Annex, the reader can find the draft project's overall Privacy Policy, which is uploaded on the project's website. Task leaders are responsible for developing any additional privacy policy needed in their tasks and activities in close collaboration with the UNITELMA. Moreover, they are responsible for appropriately adjusting and translating the templates to fit the needs and specificities of their task's activities.

Privacy Policy

LAST UPDATE: 24.10.2023

Your personal data is processed by Joint Controllers in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95 / 46 / EC (hereinafter referred to as "GDPR") and data protection legislation in our particular countries.

1. Who we are

At SUSTRACK project, accessible from <https://www.sustrack.eu>, one of our main priorities is the privacy of our visitors. This Privacy Policy document contains information about personal data that is collected and recorded by consortium members of the SUSTRACK project and how we use it.

The partners of the SUSTRACK consortium, listed below, process certain types of personal data for the purposes of the project. Each partner is responsible for the personal data they collect and process during their activities under the framework of the project:

- UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA UNITELMA SAPIENZA (ITALY)
- STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (NETHERLANDS)
- KNOWLEDGE SRL (ITALY)
- PEDAL CONSULTING SRO (SLOVAKIA)
- DBFZ DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH (GERMANY)
- UNIVERSITEIT GENT (BELGIUM)
- FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION (SPAIN)
- FVA SAS DI LOUIS FERRINI & C (ITALY)
- UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA (ITALY)
- BUNDESANSTALT FUER MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND - PRUEFUNG (GERMANY)
- FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS (SPAIN)

For further information, we can be contacted at: dataprotection@sustrack.eu.

2. How do we collect personal data?

We collect personal data both directly and indirectly:

Directly we obtain personal data directly from you in a variety of ways, including but not limited to the following cases when you:

- subscribe to our newsletter/s;
- register to attend meetings and events we host and during attendance at such events;
- establish cooperative relationships with us;
- provide professional services pursuant to our contract with the European Commission;
- participate in an interview or survey organized by us.
- Indirectly we obtain personal data from a variety of sources, including:
 - our research partners;
 - our networks and contacts;
 - public and open data sources such as public registers, news articles and internet searches;
 - social and professional networking sites (e.g., LinkedIn).

3. What type of data do we collect?

We only collect the personal data that are necessary for a proper implementation of our project, our cooperation and communication with you. These data fall into the following categories:

- contact details (name, surname, e-mail address, street address, mobile phone number, landline phone number);
- professional information (job title, organization, field of expertise);
- videos and photos during our events.

4. Basis of lawful processes

Legal Basis	Purposes
-------------	----------

Legal obligations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring our compliance with both national and European legislation as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the EU stems, • Reporting to the European Commission to comply with the project's publicity obligations.
Consent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting research (e.g., interviews, surveys); • Dissemination our project's results to different types of stakeholder; • Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our events and webinars; • log files for analytics trends, administering the site, tracking users' movement on the website, and gathering demographic information.
Contractual obligations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing online requests or queries, including responding to communications from individuals;
Legitimate interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing personal data required to solve potential legal disputes.

5. Security measures to ensure personal data protection

We continuously apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organizational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide our personnel when processing your data;
- Written contracts with organizations that process personal data on our behalf;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with our personnel;
- Back up process, antimalware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.
- Some of our partners have appointed a Data Protection Officer.

6. Sharing your personal data with third parties

We may occasionally share your personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Dropbox, Microsoft SharePoint, Google);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Dissemination services providers (e.g., MailChimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission according to our relevant contractual obligations.

SUSTRACK project's Privacy Policy does not apply to other advertisers or websites. Thus, we are advising you to consult the respective Privacy Policies of these third-party ad servers for more detailed information. It may include their practices and instructions about how to opt-out of certain options. You can choose to disable cookies through your individual browser options. To know more detailed information about cookie management with specific web browsers, it can be found at the browsers' respective websites.

7. Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, some partners may use cloud and / or marketing services from reputable providers such as SharePoint, DropBox, MailChimp, Google, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before starting using their services. With effect from 20 September 2023, the USA provides adequate guarantees in the protection of personal data based on Decision EK2023/1795.

8. Cookies

Our websites use cookies. Where cookies are used, a statement will be sent to your browser explaining the use of cookies. To learn more, please refer to our cookie policy.

Cookies are small text files which are saved on your computer, mobile phone or tablet.

They allow the website to remember your actions and preferences (such as login, language, font size and other display preferences) so you don't have to keep re-entering them whenever you come back to the site. You can control and/ or delete cookies as you wish. If you do this, however, you may need to manually adjust your preferences every time you visit a site. For more information on how to manage cookies, please visit: <http://www.aboutcookies.org/>

Third-party ad servers or ad networks use technologies like cookies, JavaScript, or Web Beacons that are used in their respective advertisements and links that appear on SUSTRACK project, which are sent directly to users' browsers. They automatically receive your IP address when this occurs. These technologies are used to measure the effectiveness of their advertising campaigns and/or to personalize the advertising content that you see on websites that you visit. Note that SUSTRACK project has no access to or control over these cookies that are used by third-party advertisers.

9. Children information

SUSTRACK project does not knowingly collect any Personal Identifiable Information from children under the age of 13. If you think that your child provided this kind of information on our website,

we strongly encourage you to contact us immediately and we will promptly remove such information from our records.

10. Your rights

We will retain your personal information only for as long as it is necessary for the purposes set out in this Privacy Policy. Under GDPR, as a data subject you have certain rights applicable to our data processing:

- The right to access to understand what personal data we process
- The right to correction of your personal data that we process
- The right to object data processing (might be limited due to other legal obligations we have)
- The right for restriction (might be limited due to other legal obligations we have)
- The right to be forgotten (might be limited due to other legal obligations we have)
- The right to withdraw consent

If you wish to be informed what personal data we hold about you, if you wish to withdraw your consent or to have your data deleted from our systems, please contact us at dataprotection@sustrack.eu.

Annex II Informed Consent Form

Text in red colour contains guidelines for adjusting this template and should be deleted.

Text included in < > and/or highlighted with yellow should be replaced with content that is suitable to the context of each activity & project as well as to the organisation seeking to obtain the consent.

Before using this template take the time to carefully read and adjust it to the needs of the activity at hand as well as to any relevant regulations and particularities applicable to your country and organisation. Specifically, this template has been developed for a data processing activity involving interviews, however you can easily adapt it to other common data processing activities such as surveys, events organizing, etc.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are:

We are < Insert Partner Name > and we are contacting you in the framework of SUSTRACK, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation funding programme. A detailed description on how SUSTRACK handles personal data is presented in the project's [Privacy Policy](#) that accompanies this Consent Form.

Project: SUSTRACK - Supporting the identification of policy priorities and recommendations for designing a sustainable track towards circular bio-based systems (GA Number 101081823).

Partner:

Organisation name: < Insert Partner Name >

Address: < Insert Partner Address >.

Phone: < Insert Partner Phone >.

E-mail: <Insert Partner Generic E-mail Address >

Responsible persons:

You may delete the line referring to the Data Protection Officer if your organisation does not have one.

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	SUSTRACK Project Manager	<Insert name of project manager>	<Insert email of project manager>
2	Interviewer	<Insert name of interviewer>	<Insert e-mail of interviewer>
3	Data Protection Officer	<Insert name of DPO >	<Insert e-mail of DPO >

What do we need from you?

Please explain in a brief paragraph (4-5 lines) the activity and its purpose under the frame of the project.

Example: We need you to participate in an interview that will be carried out by SUSTRACK with a view to validate the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy.

The interview is expected to last for no more than < Insert number of minutes > minutes. We will take written notes and we will be making a sound recording of the interview.

Please adapt the following text to accurately depict the type of personal data to be collected.

To effectively conduct this interview, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details (full name, email, phone number);
- Some basic demographics (age, gender);
- Your professional info (organization, job position, field of expertise);
- Your opinions on the subject matter.

Why do we need your data & what will we do with them?

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out the aforementioned interview and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of the interview. We also need to record your data to keep track of the interview process. The project's deliverables that will be derived by the interview will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. Your personal data will remain on our written notes (interview's transcript) and/or the sound recording we will make during the interview.

We will share your data with a few other SUSTRACK project partners that are also involved in this task and will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you gave us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project's activities (e.g., surveys, interviews, project events, SUSTRACK Advisory Board, etc.) and also to inform you about the project's progress (e.g., by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How can you withdraw your consent?

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed in the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that you do not consent to the relevant subject.)

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in an interview that will be carried out by SUSTRACK to < insert key objective of the interview >	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	My participation in future activities of SUSTRACK	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Receiving newsletters and messages regarding SUSTRACK activities	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Annex III Data Subject Request Form

Text in red colour contains guidelines for adjusting this template and should be deleted.

Text included in < > and/or highlighted with yellow should be replaced with content that is suitable to the context of each activity & project as well as to the organisation seeking to obtain the consent.

SUSTRACK

Data Subject Request Form

You may delete the data referring to the Data Protection Officer if your organisation does not have one.

Contact

<Insert name of responsible Project Manager>

<Insert name of DPO > (Data Protection Officer)

<Insert email of responsible Project Manager>

<Insert e-mail of DPO >

Data Subject Request Form

This form should be used to submit a data subject request under the provisions of the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Submitter Details

Title:	
Name:	
Address:	

Type of Request

Please select the type of request you are making:

- Consent Withdrawal*
- Access request*
- Rectification of personal data*
- Erasure of personal data*
- Restriction of processing of personal data*
- Personal data portability request*
- Objection to processing of personal data*
- Request regarding automated decision making and profiling*

Personal data involved

Request details

Request reason/justification

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Once completed, this form should be submitted via e-mail to [< Insert contact e-mail of Partner >](#) or posted to:

[< Insert Partner Name >](#)

[< Insert Partner Address >](#)

Annex IV Dataset Inventory

ID	Dataset Name	Type of Data	WP / Deliverable Link	Open or Confidential	Repository / Storage Location	PID / DOI (if open)	Reason for Confidentiality (if applicable)	Personal Data?	FAIR Status
DS1	Barriers to Transitioning to a Circular Bio-based Economy	Barrier assessment dataset	WP1 - D1.2 / D1.3	Open	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.13352885	-	No	FAIR
DS2	SUSTRACK - Knowledge Gaps	Knowledge review dataset	WP2 - D2.1	Open	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.13353519	-	No	FAIR
DS3	Appendix A - Evolution of Barriers	Barrier evolution dataset	WP1	Open	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.17266334	-	No	FAIR
DS4	SUSTRACK - Gap Analysis	Literature gap dataset	WP1 - D1.1	Open	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.13353332	-	No	FAIR
DS5	Appendix B - Ranking of Barriers	Ranking dataset	WP1 - D1.3	Open	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.17266506	-	No	FAIR
DS6	SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Indicators	Indicator database	WP2 - D2.4	Open	Zenodo + Monitoring Tool	10.5281/zenodo.17941287	-	No	FAIR
DS7	Extended Data for Insights from an	Analytical tables dataset	WP1	Open	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.17610017	-	No	FAIR

D.7.2 Data Management Plan (V2)

ID	Dataset Name	Type of Data	WP / Deliverable Link	Open or Confidential	Repository / Storage Location	PID / DOI (if open)	Reason for Confidentiality (if applicable)	Personal Data?	FAIR Status
	Extensive Multi-stakeholder Engagement								
DS8	Case Study Raw Analytical Files	Working spreadsheets	WP3	Confidential	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Internal analytical working material	No	Internal
DS9	Policy Scenario Internal Working Files	Scenario drafts	WP4	Confidential	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Intermediate modelling inputs	No	Internal
DS10	Advisory Board Contact Dataset	Contact list	WP6	Confidential	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	GDPR-protected contact data	Yes	Not shareable
DS11	Stakeholder Event Participant Lists	Event registrations	WP6	Confidential	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	GDPR-protected data	Yes	Not shareable
DS12	Newsletter Subscription Dataset	Subscriber database	WP6	Confidential	Hostinger (EU-based server)	-	GDPR-protected contact data	Yes	Not shareable
DS13	Dissemination Monitoring Raw Logs	Activity tracking	WP6	Confidential (raw)	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Raw internal monitoring files	No	Internal

D.7.2 Data Management Plan (V2)

ID	Dataset Name	Type of Data	WP / Deliverable Link	Open or Confidential	Repository / Storage Location	PID / DOI (if open)	Reason for Confidentiality (if applicable)	Personal Data?	FAIR Status
DS14	Website & Social Media Analytics	Aggregated metrics	WP6 - D6.2, D6.5	Confidential (raw)	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Raw internal monitoring files	No	Internal
DS15	Capacity-Building Training Materials	Presentations, tutorials, videos	WP5 - D5.4	Confidential (raw)	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Intermediate working files	No	Internal
DS16	Policy Priorities Evidence Base	Policy review tables	WP5 - D5.1	Confidential (raw)	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Intermediate working files	No	Internal
DS17	Policy Options & Stakeholder Recommendations	Workshop outputs	WP5 - D5.3	Confidential (raw)	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Intermediate working files	No	Internal
DS18	Policy Recommendations	Consolidated recommendations	WP5 - D5.2 / D5.5	Confidential (raw)	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Intermediate working files	No	Internal
DS19	Project Management QA Files	Internal coordination docs	WP7	Confidential (raw)	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Internal management documentation	No	Internal
DS20	GEM Model Input Data	Macroeconomic statistics	WP4 - D4.2	Confidential (raw)	Consortium secure cloud repository	-	Intermediate working files	No	Internal

Project Consortium

